

Floral characters of CMS lines under two environments. Bangalore, India. 1991 DS and WS.

CMS line	Anther length (mm)		Anther breadth (mm)		Anther size (mm ²)		Stigma length (mm)		Stigma breadth (mm)		Stigma size (mm ²)		Style length (mm)		Pollen sterility (%)		Anthesis duration (min)	
	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS	1991 DS	1991 WS
V20 A	2.30	1.50	0.45	0.32	0.92	0.48	1.66	2.11	0.56	0.41	1.86	1.73	0.53	0.69	100.0	99.8	273	285
IR54752 A	2.21	1.83	0.65	0.40	1.46	0.73	1.52	1.69	0.60	0.43	1.82	1.45	0.84	0.86	98.8	100.0	238	250
IMA	2.19	1.63	0.64	0.33	1.40	0.54	1.33	1.62	0.43	0.37	1.14	1.20	0.83	0.65	2.8	37.0	250	205
Mangala A	1.97	2.13	0.42	0.41	0.83	0.87	1.25	1.46	0.42	0.33	1.05	0.96	0.55	0.79	4.5	13.8	205	195
Pushpa A	2.40	1.76	0.41	0.38	0.98	0.67	1.61	1.50	0.42	0.31	1.35	0.93	0.55	1.00	1.5	17.0	211	185
PMS1 A	1.90	1.78	0.39	0.35	0.74	0.62	1.36	1.46	0.43	0.31	1.17	0.91	0.63	0.63	100.0	69.0	256	260
PMS2 A	1.84	1.34	0.39	0.33	0.72	0.48	1.36	1.27	0.43	0.31	1.17	0.79	0.92	0.95	98.5	98.0	251	260
PMS3 A	1.98	1.74	0.37	0.30	0.74	0.52	1.50	1.33	0.55	0.33	1.65	0.88	0.69	0.66	100.0	100.0	284	290
PMS4 A	1.75	1.36	0.35	0.34	0.63	0.63	1.40	1.65	0.44	0.36	1.23	1.19	0.72	0.77	98.2	74.0	255	285
PMS5 A	2.02	1.73	0.34	0.38	0.69	0.66	1.36	1.45	0.44	0.33	1.20	0.96	0.76	0.71	96.5	100.0	251	260
PMS6 A	1.99	1.70	0.30	0.29	0.60	0.49	1.43	1.33	0.43	0.33	1.23	0.88	0.73	0.82	88.6	100.0	208	218
PMS7 A	2.37	1.91	0.43	0.33	1.01	0.63	1.55	1.45	0.54	0.33	1.67	0.96	0.72	0.90	98.0	99.2	256	260
PMS8 A	1.96	1.69	0.37	0.26	0.73	0.44	1.58	1.37	0.47	0.33	1.49	0.90	0.74	0.86	99.3	98.9	246	265
PMS9 A	2.23	1.89	0.45	0.33	1.00	0.62	1.58	1.35	0.53	0.37	1.67	0.97	0.80	0.61	99.0	100.0	285	290
PMS10 A	1.85	1.89	0.36	0.37	0.67	0.62	1.52	1.57	0.53	0.37	1.61	1.16	0.62	0.65	97.0	100.0	257	265
Mean	2.05	1.76	0.43	0.34	0.87	0.60	1.47	1.50	0.48	0.35	1.42	1.06	0.71	0.77	78.84	80.45	248.49	251.63
Range	0.64	0.79	0.35	0.15	0.86	0.43	0.41	0.84	0.18	0.12	0.81	0.94	0.39	0.39	98.5	86.2	80.0	105.0
CV (%)	9.39	10.52	23.68	12.12	29.94	18.78	8.20	13.82	13.00	10.43	19.17	23.81	16.26	16.18	49.96	39.68	9.88	13.76
SE (m)	0.05	0.05	0.025	0.011	0.067	0.03	0.03	0.054	0.028	0.009	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03	10.17	8.22	6.34	8.93

between opening of the first spikelet in the main panicle in the morning and closing of all spikelets in that panicle.

Genotypes performed very differently under the two environments (see table). In general, the mean values for anther length, anther breadth, anther size, stigma breadth, and stigma size were greater in DS than in WS, while mean values for stigma length and pollen sterility were

greater in WS than in DS. No difference was observed between the environments for anthesis duration. Anthesis, however, started earlier (0900 h) in DS than in WS (1100 h).

Variability (indicated by range and coefficient of variation) for anther breadth, anther size, stigma breadth, and pollen sterility was higher in DS than in WS; for anther length, stigma length,

stigma size, style length, and anthesis duration, variability was higher in WS than in DS. Expression of floral traits influencing outcrossing was generally better in DS than in WS.

Results suggest that it is advantageous to produce hybrid rice seed during DS because more floral traits are better expressed than during WS. ■

Restorers and maintainers for MS 577 A and wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterility system

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Ninety-six rice genotypes were crossed with six cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines possessing cytoplasmic male sterility system of MS 577 A and 24 genotypes with four wild abortive (WA)-type CMS lines, resulting in 252 F₁s with 577 A cytoplasm and 39 F₁s with WA cytoplasm. Based on spikelet fertility of these hybrids, genotypes were classified as restorers (>80%), partial restorers

(10-80%), and maintainers (<10%).

None of the 96 genotypes completely restored the fertility of 577 A. IR36, IR13146-45, IET7191, Karna, Milyang 54, and Nucleoriza, however, were found to be partial restorers.

Of the 18 IRRI genotypes evaluated, 10 were identified as restorers for WA CMS lines (IR8, IR36, IR60, IR13146-45, IR15324-13, IR20226-24, IR21543-2-1-22, IR27280, IR22810-60, and IR31916-9), 6 as partial restorers, and 1 as a maintainer (IR21916-128). Among other genotypes, 3 were identified as restorers (Cornell culture, ARC11353, and RP101-3-129), 2 as partial restorers, and 1 as a maintainer (local variety CTH1). ■

Yield potential

Performance of anaerobically direct seeded rice plants in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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Most farmers in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam practice direct seeding. Improved rice cultivars are used, but they were selected for use in the transplanting system. Introducing cultivars suitable for direct seeding may benefit farmers. We conducted this study to identify desirable traits for high-yielding direct seeded rice.

Table 1. Crop establishment, growth parameters, grain yield, and yield components of direct seeded rice in the Mekong Delta.^a CLRRRI, 1993 wet season.

Cultivar	Seedlings ^b / m ² (no.)	TDM ^b at flowering (g/m ²)	TDM ^b at maturity (g/m ²)	LAI ^b at flowering	Harvest index ^b (%)	Spikelets/ m ² (no.× 10 ³)	Panicles ^c / m ² (no.)	Spikelets ^c / panicle (no.)	Filled spikelets ^c (%)	1,000 grain weight ^c (g)	Yield ^a (t/ha)
IR41996-50-2-1-3	400 a	455 c	740 b	2.20 b	47.0 a	23.4 c	527 a	44 d	76.6 a	29.5 a	2.87 d
IR52341-60-1-2-1	406 a	561 c	953 ab	1.53 c	47.0 a	28.9 bc	446 a	65 c	73.9 a	27.5 b	3.77 bcd
IR31802-48-2-2-2	401 a	455 c	811 b	1.93 bc	41.0 b	37.1 b	527 a	70 c	63.4 b	24.0 c	3.40 cd
MTL 114 (check)	375 b	734 b	1134 a	3.47 a	44.0 ab	39.1 b	479 a	82 c	73.8 a	27.7 b	4.80 abc
MTL 103 (check)	379 b	713 b	1020 ab	3.50 a	47.0 a	36.5 b	471 a	77 c	80.2 a	28.1 b	5.13 ab
BR736-20-3-1	407 a	870 a	1110 a	3.87 a	42.0 ab	55.4 a	410 a	135 a	78.7 a	21.5 e	5.20 ab
BR1870-67-1-3	400 a	840 a	1114 a	4.00 a	45.0 ab	55.8 a	442 a	126 b	80.3 a	22.7 d	5.83 a

^aMeans in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^bSampled from 0.5 m² per plot. ^cAnalyzed from 20 panicles per plot. ^dHarvested from 5 m² per plot.

Table 2. Coefficients of simple linear correlations between the characters associated with grain yield.^a

Character	Two	Three	Four	Five	Six	Seven	Eight	Nine	Ten	Eleven
One	-0.17	-0.33	0.36	-0.21	0.19	0.12	-0.14	-0.48	-0.20	-0.28
Two		0.94**	0.91**	-0.84*	0.90**	0.86*	0.67*	-0.55	-0.15	0.95**
Three			0.79*	-0.80*	0.78*	0.75	0.51	-0.42	-0.14	0.92**
Four				-0.55	0.79*	0.80*	0.66	-0.45	-0.16	0.90**
Five					-0.79*	-0.69	-0.60	0.53	0.02	-0.75
Six						0.98**	0.42	-0.86*	-0.45	0.84*
Seven							0.33	-0.88**	-0.53	0.84*
Eight								0.02	0.55	0.62
Nine									0.73	-0.52
Ten										-0.10

^a* = significant at the 5% level; ** = significant at the 1% level. 1 = seedlings (no./m²), 2 = TDM accumulation at flowering, 3 = TDM accumulation at maturity, 4 = LAI at flowering, 5 = panicles (no./m²), 6 = spikelets (no./panicle), 7 = spikelets (no./m²), 8 = filled spikelets (%), 9 = 1,000-grain weight, 10 = harvest index, 11 = yield.

Seven cultivars were used, five of which are tolerant of soil anaerobiosis during seedling establishment. The other two are local checks (Table 1). Pregerminated seeds (2 d old) were sown at 400 seeds/m² (about 100 kg/ha) immediately after puddling the soil (pH 5.2, 0.04% total P, 3.2% organic C, and 0.26% total N). Seeds were beneath the soil surface. A herbicide, Sofit, was sprayed 3 d after sowing (DAS). Fertilizer was applied at 60-17-25 kg NPK/ha at 10 DAS, 30 kg N/ha at 30 DAS, and 60 kg N/ha at 60 DAS. The experiment was laid out in a

randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 20 m².

Number of seedlings established was higher for anaerobic cultivars than for checks. Yields of BR1870-67-1-3 and BR736-20-3-1 were the same as those of the checks, and higher than those of IR52341-60-1-2-1, IR31802-48-2-2-2, and IR41996-50-2-1-3. Difference in yield was due to the difference in total dry matter (TDM) accumulation at maturity and not in harvest index (HI) (Table 1). BR1870-67-1-3 and BR736-20-3-1 had large panicle size, indicated

by the high spikelet number/panicle. Although BR1870-67-1-3 and BR736-20-3-1 had more spikelets/m², they did not outyield checks significantly because their 1,000-grain weights were small.

Correlation analysis showed that the grain yield highly correlated with TDM accumulation at flowering and harvest, spikelets/panicle, spikelets/m², and leaf area index (LAI) at flowering (Table 2).

The significant correlation between spikelets/m² and spikelets/panicle ($r = 0.98^{**}$) indicated that big panicles are important for obtaining a large number of spikelets per unit land area.

The yield recorded for BR1870-67-1-3 was higher than the mean (4.3 t/ha) for the past 7 yr at CLRRRI during the wet season under transplanting (80-25-18 kg NPK/ha). The physiological and morphological traits required for high-yielding direct seeded rice in the Mekong Delta in the wet season seem to be high TDM accumulation at flowering and harvest, LAI at flowering of about 4, and large panicle size. These characters may be considered when breeding rice for direct seeding in the Mekong Delta. ■

Simulating rice leaffolder feeding effects on yield using MACROS

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The rice leaffolder (LF), *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, can affect yield by reducing

leaf area. Most previous attempts to relate yield to leaf area removed were probably too simplistic. Systems analysis and simulation approaches may improve our understanding of this relationship.

We conducted an experiment to quantify the reduction in leaf area due to LF feeding. We incorporated the actual

leaf consumption into the MACROS rice model and predicted yield loss at different larval densities and crop ages.

Destructive weekly samplings were taken from five hills of IR36. A LICOR LI-3000 leaf area meter was used to measure total leaf area and leaf area damaged in 1-× 1-m plots infested with 3